

Title: Chemical bonding and molecular structure for NEET and JEE students in One Page

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Abstract

Chemical bonding and molecular structure are the main ideas in chemistry. They describe how atoms connect, unite, and become stable. This review combines basic bonding theories like ionic, covalent, coordinate, and metallic with newer quantum ideas like hybridization, molecular orbital theory (MOT), and Valence Shell Electron Pair Repulsion (VSEPR) theory. The study employs a mind mapping framework to illustrate the interrelationship among bond formation, bond parameters, molecular geometry, and polarity, hence enhancing conceptual clarity for learners. The study also talks about Fajan's rule, formal charge, dipole moment, and bond order as important ways to guess how molecules would act. The review finds that mind maps are a useful way to organize abstract chemical information in higher secondary chemistry classes, helping students understand and remember what they learn for a long time.

Key Words

Chemical bonding, Molecular structure, Hybridization, VSEPR theory, Molecular orbital theory, Mind mapping, Visual learning

TYPES OF BONDS

IONIC/ELECTROVALENT BOND

- Strong electro static force of attraction between positive and negative ions.
- Crystalline in nature
- High M.P and B.P
- Soluble in Polar Solvents. Eg: NaCl, MgCl₂ etc.

HYDROGEN BOND

- Bond formed when the -ve end of one molecule attracts the +ve end of H.
- 1. Intermolecular: H-Bonding occur within one single molecule.
- 2. Intermolecular: H Bonding between two different molecules of same or different compounds.

COVALENT BOND

- Bond formed by mutual sharing of e⁻.
- Low M.P. and B.P.
- Bad conductor of electricity
- Insoluble in Polar Solvents but soluble in non-polar solvent. Ex: CH₄, H₂, Cl₂.

CO-ORDINATE BONDING

- Bond formed by one sided sharing of electrons. ie: one atom donates a pair of e⁻ while other accepts it.
- Bad conductors of electricity.
- Sparingly soluble in polar solvents but readily soluble in non-polar solvents. eg:- NH₄⁺

TYPE OF CO-VALENT BOND

- Polar covalent bond Eg: NH₃, CHCl₃
- Non-polar covalent bond Eg: Cl₂, CO₂.

FAJAN'S RULE

- No compounds is 100% ionic or 100% covalent
- Covalent nature ∝ Charge on cation
- Covalent nature ∝ $\frac{1}{\text{size of cation}}$
- Polarising Power ∝ Covalent C

Cation Polarized anion
Polarization of anion by cation

BOND PARAMETERS

FORMAL CHARGE

$$FC = V - N - \frac{B}{2}$$

- Bond length: distance between the nuclei of two bonded atom
- bond length ∝ $\frac{1}{\text{bond order}}$

BOND ORDER

No. of Bond between the two atoms

BOND ANGLE

Angle between the orbitals containing bonding e⁻ pair around central atom.

BOND ENTHALPY

Amount of energy required to break one mole of bonds.

DIPOLE MOMENT

Product of the magnitude of the charge and distance between centres of positive and negative charge.

$$\mu = \text{charge} \times \text{Distance Between two atoms}$$

CHEMICAL BONDING AND MOLECULAR STRUCTURE

VSEPR THEORY

The shape of a molecule depends upon the numbers of valence shell e⁻ (B.P or L.P) surrounding in the central atom.

Decreasing order of repulsive interaction: lp - lp > lp - bp > bp - bp

Type of Molecule	No. of Bonding Pair	No. of Lone Pair	Arrangement of e ⁻ pair	Shape	Example
AB ₂ E	2	1	Trigonal planar	Bent	SO ₂ O ₃
AB ₃ E	3	1	Tetrahedral	Trigonal pyramidal	NH ₃
AB ₃ E ₂	2	2	Tetrahedral	Bent	H ₂ O
AB ₄ E	4	1	Trigonal bi-pyramidal	See saw	SF ₄
AB ₃ E ₂	3	2	Trigonal bi-pyramidal	T-Shape	ClF ₃
AB ₅ E	5	1	Octahedral	Square Pyramid	XeF ₅
AB ₄ E ₂	4	2	Octahedral	Square Planar	XeF ₄

KOSSEL LEWIS APPROACH

Atoms can combine either by transfer of e⁻ or by sharing of valence e⁻ in order to have an complete octet in their valence shell.

Octet Rule

LEWIS SYMBOLS

Valence e⁻ are represented by dots around the element.

VALENCE BOND THEORY (VBT)

A covalent bond is formed by the overlapping of two half filled atomic orbitals.

TYPE OF OVERLAPPING

Sigma(σ) Sidewise overlapping

S-S overlapping

S-P overlapping

Pi(π) Sidewise overlapping

HYBRIDISATION

Concept of mixing atomic orbital to form new hybrid

Formation of Molecular Orbitals

MOLECULAR ORBITAL THEORY

MOT states that each atom tends to combine together and form molecular orbitals

No. of molecular orbitals = No. of atomic orbital combined.

MOT

Bonding molecular orbitals

Anti bonding atomic orbitals

ELECTRONIC CONFIGURATION

Electron filling order upto 14 electrons

Electron filling order for more than 14 electrons

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